

1 **An HBIM approach for the preventive conservation of historical constructions:**
2 **application to the Historical Library of Salamanca**

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21
22 **Abstract**

23 This work presents an approach for the preventive conservation of historical constructions by
24 means of HBIM strategies. To this end, the methodology exploits the latest advances in inspection
25 protocols, digitalization tools -by means of the novel back-pack mapping systems- as well as
26 wireless monitoring networks. All this information is integrated in the HBIM environment by
27 using ad-hoc families and interoperable communication protocols that allow obtaining a complete
28 knowledge of the conservation status of the site. Additionally, the approach uses key performance
29 indicators in order to evaluate the environmental conditions of the different assets presented in
30 the site. All these features have been validated in one of the most representative heritage buildings
31 in Spain: The General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca.

32 **Keywords:** Cultural Heritage, Preventive Conservation; Historical Building Information
33 Modelling, Internet of Things, Monitoring Network, Wearable Mobile Mapping System

34 **1. Introduction**

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36 Nowadays preventive conservation could be considered the most effective preservation approach
37 for heritage buildings. This strategy is able to save around 40-70% of the total maintenance costs
38 in contrast with traditional remedial approaches by avoiding major interventions and promoting
39 the use of monitoring networks as well as periodic inspections [1]. However, there are several
40 challenges that turn difficult its effective implementation, requiring the development of
41 standardized and integrated protocols for documenting and managing all the information needed
42 to preserve the site. In this context, BIM-based strategies have been placed in as one of the most
43 promising technologies. These approaches aim at improving the building life-cycle process by
44 introducing the concept of interoperability, increasing cost- and time-effectiveness as well as
45 improving the communication between agents [2]. In the context of built cultural heritage, this
46 approach is commonly named as HBIM (Historic Building Information Modelling). It is emerging
47 as a new management system, focused on digitalizing historic structures by creating full physical
48 models populated with meaningful attributes, namely the construction system, constituent
49 materials, existing damages, monitored quantities or maintenance costs among others [3–6]. This
50 approach offers several advantages compared to traditional methods, such as: i) centralization of
51 information; ii) analysis of the different interventions carried out and; iii) fluid communication
52 between agents. This set of advantages makes possible the use of HBIM approaches for structural
53 analysis [7,8], damage assessment [4–6,9], restoration [6], documentation [10] and digital
54 representation[11], requiring all the appropriate definition of the different elements. This
55 definition needs of establishing a set of rules, which could be grouped in: i) the Level of Detail
56 (LoD) and; ii) the Level of Information (LoI).

57 The first level of definition demands the 3D modelling of the elements. In this context Murphy et
58 al. [12] propose using remote sensing approaches to capture the data, enabling to create accurate
59 digital replicas of the building and its assets. This issue is especially important in historical
60 constructions since these elements -construction or not- are often unique pieces with specific
61 geometrical features. Within this context, it is possible to find plenty of applications on which the

62 laser scanning and photogrammetric approaches are used to digitalize historical sites for HBIM
63 applications [10,12,13]. Besides the aforementioned advantages of these solutions, digitalizing
64 heritage sites usually requires the use of a large number of images or scan stations, turning time
65 consuming and involving a possible error accumulation along the network [14]. To cope with
66 these limitations, hybrid solutions, such as the mobile mapping systems (MMSs), have emerged
67 in the last few years. Among the MMSs systems available nowadays, the wearable mobile laser
68 systems (WMLS) have been placed in a privilege position for capturing cultural heritage scenarios
69 [14,15]. This solution combines a 2D laser scanning technology and an inertial measurement unit
70 (IMU) in a portable device which could be handled by a unique operator. The system acquires
71 information while the operator is walking around the heritage site. Then, the 3D point cloud is
72 created by applying the Simultaneous Location and Mapping algorithm (SLAM) [16]. According
73 to di-Filippo et al. [14] and Sánchez-Aparicio et al. [17], this system is ten time faster than laser
74 scanning procedures, providing accuracies that range from 1 to 3 cm.

75 As stated by Diara and Rinaudo (2019) [18], HBIM models extend the possibilities of CAD
76 models by adding semantic relations between the 3D objects and information. This relation could
77 be understood as the LoI of the object, demanding the proper definition of materials or
78 degradation processes among others. For example, Brumana et al. [19] uses custom properties in
79 the objects to map the damages presented in the building, increasing the objects' LoI by adding
80 historical information. Quattrini et al.[20] proposes the use of shared parameters to establish the
81 same LoI for different HBIM elements. According to Azenha et al. [21], external sources, such
82 as 360 images and laser-scanning data, could be used in this group to complement the geometrical
83 definition of the objects.

84 Complementary to these considerations, the diagnosis and preventive conservation of cultural
85 heritage sites require the use of monitoring networks to evaluate relevant parameters along the
86 time. These analysis allow to understand the interferences between the assets and their
87 environment [2] or even to evaluate the structural condition of the building, including the possible
88 relation between these parameters and the environmental ones [22]. The first of these aspects is

89 especially relevant in museums and libraries due to the use of active building conditioning
90 systems that control critical variables for the conservation of assets such as the temperature,
91 humidity or luminosity among others [23]. However, the great amount of data generated could be
92 hardly interpreted by non-expert users [24]. To cope with this limitation, several authors propose
93 the application of the so-called Key Performance Indicators (KPI). These indexes are commonly
94 used for a quick and easily readable assessment of heritage structures [22] as well as for evaluating
95 the bioclimatic conditions in museums and libraries [25,26].

96 Under the previously exposed basis, this work shows an HBIM methodology for the preventive
97 conservation of heritage sites. This methodology integrates geometrical data coming from a
98 WMMS and the information derived from a monitoring network with the standardized inspection
99 protocols developed by the European initiative HeritageCare [27,28]. This initiative attempts to
100 implement standardized protocols for preventive conservation. These protocols are articulated in
101 a total of three complementary levels: i) the Service Level 1 that aim at providing a rapid condition
102 screening of the heritage site; ii) the Service Level 2 that use Web-GIS tool for providing an
103 extended knowledge of the site and its assets and; iii) the Service Level 3 that integrated all the
104 data in a HBIM environment. For more details about these Service Levels reader refers to
105 Masciotta et al. [27]. More specifically, this work will show the results obtained during the
106 implementation of the third service level in one of the Spanish pilot cases: The Historical Library
107 of the University of Salamanca. This implementation gives a step-forward in the current
108 preventive conservation policies of the Library based on the work carried out by Sánchez-
109 Aparicio et al. 2020 [29]. In this work a new Web-GIS platform, based on the use of 360° images
110 and a geospatial database, is developed, corresponding with the second service level of
111 conservation. This platform is mainly focused to the manager of the site, plotting the essential
112 information for the preventive conservation of the site by means of easy-readable reports as well
113 as the use of KPI based on a unique tolerance defined by the guideline PAS 198:2012 [30]. The
114 main novelties of this work in comparison with this one are: i) the use of HBIM approaches
115 instead of GIS methods for the management of information related with the constructions

116 elements and the assets placed within the Library; ii) an improvement in the use of KPI for
117 preventive conservation by exploiting the data coming from the BIM families as well as a set of
118 tolerances in accordance with the type of material presented; iii) the capacity of filtering the assets
119 with respect to the type of damage presented or its conservation risk and; iv) the possibility of
120 downloading technical information related with the monitoring network.

121 According to this, the paper is structured as follows: after this initial Introduction, Section 2
122 describes the materials and methods used for the implementation of the preventive conservation
123 system. Section 3 exposes the experimental results obtained. Finally, the conclusions and future
124 perspectives are drawn in Section 4.

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126 **2. Material and Methods**

127 The proposed HBIM methodology will be based on three interconnected steps (Figure 1): i) the
128 3D digitalization of the heritage site by means of WMMS; ii) the monitoring of the main
129 bioclimatic parameters for the preventive conservation of the assets placed within the library and;
130 iii) an HBIM model that manages the information derived from the previous steps and the
131 information related to the assets. Additionally, the HBIM automatically computes and stores
132 different KPI to evaluate the bioclimatic conditions in each asset according to its materials.

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2.1. Digitalization system

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The WMMS used for the present work was the ZEB-REVO back-pack mapping system. This device, commercialized by the GeoSLAM company [31], comprises a 2D rotating laser scanner head Hokuyo UTM-30LX-F (Hokuyo Automatic Co., Ltd. Osaka, Japan) rigidly coupled to an IMU on a rotary engine. The data captured by these sensors is stored in a processing unit placed in a small backpack (Figure 2). The 3D point cloud is generated by combining the information coming from the scanning head with that from the IMU sensor. To this end, the full SLAM approach of the robotic operative system (ROS) library is used [32]. This approach uses an incremental and interactive procedure to register the segments captured by the scanning head one-by-one. Finally, this registration is refined following a similar framework to the well-known Iterative Closest Point algorithm. The error accumulation derived from the incremental procedure is minimized by a global registration on the basis that the starting and ending points are the same (closed-loop solution).

151 This sensor has a default range of 0.60-30m for indoors environments and 0.60 to 15 m for outdoor
 152 ones, capturing 40,000 points per second (Table 1). Additionally, to the scanning head, the device
 153 has a GoPro camera that allows recording a video when the laser is capturing the scene. The
 154 manufacturer ensures an accuracy of 1–3 cm for a 10-min scan, with the closing of a single loop
 155 [33]. Further detailed specifications of this device are included in Table 1

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Table 1. Zeb-Revo Specifications

WMLS Zeb REVO	
Measuring principle	Time of flight
Operating time	4 hours
Field of view	270° (H) x 360° (V)
Wavelength (nm)	905
Scanner resolution (°)	0.625 H x 1.8 V
Orientations system	MEMS IMU
Scanner dimensions (mm)	86 x 113 x 287
Total weight (kg)	4.10
Scanner weight (kg)	1.00
Dimensions (mm)	220 x 180 x 470
Working range (m)	0.60-30 m indoors 0.60-15 m outdoors
Measurement rate	40,000 points per second
Accuracy (cm)	1 - 3

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Figure 2. WMMS used: a) user working with the wearable laser scan (Zeb-Revo). b) Zeb-Revo equipment

161 2.2 Monitoring system

162 In parallel to the digitalization of the site, a monitoring network was installed (Figure 3). The aim
163 was understanding the conservation needs of the indoor assets of the Library. This monitoring
164 network focused on measuring the main bioclimatic parameters by means of the commercial
165 system MHS (Monitoring Heritage System) [34]. This monitoring system has been developed by
166 the Santa Maria La Real Foundation (<https://www.santamarialareal.org/>), highlighting for its
167 minimal visual impact and great autonomy. The number, location and type of node depend on the
168 specific needs, thereby requiring a pre-monitoring stage to define them property. Table 2 shows
169 the general specification of the nodes used by this monitoring network.

170 Table 2. Technical specifications of the nodes used
171 in the monitoring network

Technical specifications	Values
Communication protocol	ZigBee
Frequency	900 MHz or 2.4 GHz
Programming interface	JTAG/Bootloader
Input / Output	Analogical/Digital
Communication protocols	I2C/ADC/SPI
Energy supply	5V by means of a converter 3.6V AA batteries
Signal sensitivity	Up to -110 dBm
Connexion topology	Star / Tree / Mesh
Working temperature	-20 °C/ +70°C
Limit humidity	80%

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173 The information captured by the local nodes is transmitted to a central node through a Zigbee
174 communication protocol with a bandwidth from 900 MHz to 2.4 GHz. Finally, this information
175 is sent to a dedicated server and can be consulted through a web-based application, as shown in
176 Figure 3.

Figure 3. Scheme of the monitoring network implemented.

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2.3 Definition of the HBIM

181 Even though the relevance of HBIM within the context of historical constructions is assumed, the

182 BIM methodology has been mainly oriented to new buildings, thereby not having a standard

183 consensus for the historic ones yet [35]. This issue makes that some aspects, such as the Level of

184 Detail (LoD) or the Level of Information (LoI), should be considered as critical. The LoD

185 determines the graphic aspect of the assets, such as geometry, location in the building, size or

186 orientation; while the LoI stores relevant but non-geometrical information of the assets, such as

187 maintenance data, monitoring data, manufacturer information, inspection periods or additional

188 images. In HBIM works objects have so many details difficult to model with unique and non-

189 parametric shapes, specially the ornamental parts, so depending on the purpose of the HBIM it is

190 necessary a higher LoD or a lower LoD. Under this basis, and taking into account that bioclimatic

191 conditions are the main risk for the proper conservation of the assets placed within the Library,

192 the following criteria was adopted: i) a low LoD and; ii) a high LoI. Table 3 shows the different

193 LoD and LoI adopted for each family in accordance with the recommendations exposed by
 194 Barmes [36] as well as the international guideline G202TM – 2013 [37] and the Spanish
 195 recommendations exposed in the Spanish Chapter of BIM Forum [38].

196 Table 3. Level of Detail and Level of Information adopted
 197 for each family included in the HBIM model in accordance with the guideline G202TM-2013 and the
 198 Spanish Chapter of BIM Forum.

Type of object	Level of Detail	Level of Information
Construction elements	300	400
	Elements properly represented in terms of quantity, size, shape, location and orientation	Technical system specification, including components to allow product selection
Assets	300	500
	Elements properly represented in terms of quantity, size, shape, location and orientation	Detailed specification of manufacturer’s product, testing operation and maintenance
Nodes	200	500
	Generic system, object, or assembly with approximate quantities, size, shape, location, and orientation	Detailed specification of manufacturer’s product, testing operation and maintenance
Damages	200	500
	Generic system, object, or assembly with approximate quantities, size, shape, location, and orientation	Detailed specification of manufacturer’s product, testing operation and maintenance

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 200 On the one hand, the geometry of each object (LoD) was based on the data provided by the
 201 WMMS, simplifying ornamental elements as well as assuming ideal shapes for the arches and the
 202 vault, but defining properly the materials presented on them. The pass from the point cloud to the
 203 CAD model was carried out by means of reverse engineering procedures, similar to those showed
 204 by Bautista de Castro et al [39] or Sánchez-Aparicio et al [40]. The geometrical information
 205 omitted, e.g. the ornamental parts, was included in the LoI of each object.

206 In contrast to this low LoD, the current methodology introduces an exhaustive LoI to handle the
 207 properties of each material, changes suffered, or damages presented. In order to establish this LoI
 208 correctly to each object, the elements were classified depending on the information each one needs

209 into 4 main groups (Figure 4) (Table 3): i) construction elements; ii) assets; iii) nodes; iv)
210 damages.

211 All this graphical and non-graphical information was translated into the open exchange format
212 IFC4 (Industry Foundation Classes version 4), thereby ensuring the inter-operability between
213 different tools and HBIM scalability. IFC allows to export any kind of information so that all the
214 custom parameters created for the new assets, damages and nodes are well contemplated.

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Figure 4. Object classification proposed.

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2.3.1 Construction elements

220 According to the purpose of the HBIM, only the inner envelop of the library was modelled. In
221 this sense it was necessary to take into consideration four different types of families: i) masonry
222 walls; ii) vaults and arches; iii) windows and; iv) slab. The information inserted in the walls,
223 arches and vaults has been defined with the aim of including all the relevant construction
224 parameters, namely (Figure 5): i) number of leaves; ii) material used in each leaf; iii) finishing
225 material. The main door and the windows, made up by glasses, include the following information
226 labels: i) number of layers; ii) type of glass in each layer and; iii) type of frame. Finally, the timber
227 floor was defined by the following tabs: i) number of joint's sets; ii) type of wood; and iii)
228 finishing material.

229 Complementarily, these families include all the relevant information with respect to its
 230 conservation state. In this sense, the following fields were included: i) previous interventions; ii)
 231 last interventions date and iii) conservation state. Due to simplifications during the geometrical
 232 modelling, each family includes the possibility of inserting different images that allow
 233 complementing the spatial definition of the element defined.

Parameter Name	IFC Type data	Notes
Geometric Data		
Height	IFCReal	Example: 1.20 m
Length	IFCReal	Example: 4.23 m
Thickness	IFCReal	Example: 0.65 m
Material Characterization		
Stone Type	IFCText	Example: Granite
Stone Origin	IFCText	Only if known
Stone Density	IFCReal / IFCMassDensityMeasure	Kg / m3
Other Materials	IFCText	If it is known the presence of other materials
Outdoor Finishing System	IFCText	Finished system of exterior wall
Indoor Finishing System	IFCText	Finished system of interior wall
Facade Composition	IFC Text	Example: 1Leaf / 2Leafs
Conservation Data		
Previous Intervention	IFCText	Type of intervention
Last Intervention Date	IFCText	Date last intervention
Conservation State	IFCText	Good, Medium, Bad
Photographic Survey	IfcRelAssociates	Link to Image

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2.3.2 Damages

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Figure 5. Construction elements family structure with the IFC parameters added to complete the information.

Damages are represented by means of custom patch-objects, as proposed Sousa et al. [41]. Path-objects are geometrically simple elements with a low LoD, but with a very complete LoI. In this sense the geometry of each damage is modelled by means of rectangular patches attached to some

243 construction element or asset. Each patch has different size and colour depending on the affected
244 area and relevance of the damage (Figure 6a). The LoI of this object includes an exhaustive
245 definition of the damage according to the damage atlas developed within the framework of the
246 HeritageCare project [27,28]. This atlas classifies each damage according to a three-level system,
247 i.e. class of damage, sub-class of damage and sub-sub-class of damage. Moreover, these objects
248 include: i) a condition classification; ii) a status risk; iii) urgency to take an action; and iv) affected
249 area. It is worth mentioning that the third information label depends on the values adopted by the
250 status risk (Table 4). The fourth information label refers to the extension of the damage, allowing
251 the user to enter the metric value of the damage as the percentage of the affected area with respect
252 to the constructive element (HeritageCARE approach) [27]. In the case of cracks, two metric
253 parameters are used: i) the length of the crack and; ii) the aperture of the crack. These parameters
254 allow to monitor the evolution of the damage through time.

255 Table 4. Options for the labels condition classification and status risk. The text between brackets is the
256 value assigned to the third information label.

Label	Values
Condition classification	Good
	Fair
	Poor
	Bad
Status risk	Low (long term)
	Moderate (intermediate term)
	High (short term)
	Severe (urgent and immediate)

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Figure 6. Damage and node objects within the HBIM model. a) Two damages with different risk attached in a construction element. b) Node patch placed in the library and its parameters

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2.3.3 Assets

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Both the main and removable assets have been represented by instances of new families, created

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ad-hoc for this job. The families have their own geometric parameters, which are different for

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each object type. However, in order to make it reusable and scalable, these families show the

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same conservation and preventive information parameters. These new set of parameters have been

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structured in two groups as follows (Figure 7): i) the data related with the identification and

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location of the assets and; ii) the data related with the damage presented in the asset.

Name ID	Shelving	
Category	Removable Asset	
Parameter Name	IFC Type data	Notes
Geometric Data		
Height	IFCReal	Example: 1.20 m
Length	IFCReal	Example: 4.23 m
Depth	IFCReal	Example: 0.65 m
Shelves Number	IFCInteger	Example: 1 - 2 - 3
Shelves gap Separation	IFCReal	Example: 0.40 m - 0.50 m
Identification Data		
Asset ID	IFCInteger	Example: 121
Asset Name	IFCText	Example: Shelving with original books
Asset Code	IFCInteger	Example: 111
Asset Category	IFCText	Example: Furniture
Inspection Periods	IFCDate	Date of known inspections
Owner Name	IFCText	Owner's name if known
Owner Contact	IFCText	Telephone to contact
Changes / Modifications	IFC Text	Kind of changes suffered for the asset
Short description	IFCText	Description of the asset
Material	IFC Text	Main Material
Support Material	IFC Text	If exist any other material
Techniques Manufacture	IFC Text	Types of tools used
Photographic Survey	IfcRelAssociates	Link to the image of the asset
Damages Assesment		
Class of Damage	IFCText	Example: Biological Colonization
Sub-Class of Damage	IFCText	Example: Rot
Sub-Sub-Class of Damage	IFCText	Example: White rot
Condition Classification	IFCText	Example: Good, Fair, Poor, Bad
Symptoms	IFCText	Example: No Symptoms, Minor Symptoms
Condition Grade	IFCText	Example: In good condition, in fair condition
Extent	IFCReal	Example: 10.2 %
Length *	IFCReal	Example: 0.52 m
Aperture *	IFCReal	Example: 0.05 m
Condition Risk	IFCText	Example: Low, Medium, High
Urgency Risk	IFCText	Example: Long Term, Intermediate Term
Status	IFCInteger	Example: 1, 2, 3

Figure 7. Asset family structure with the IFC parameters for the asset, including conservation and preventive ones, created ad-hoc for the HBIM. In the upper right is the geometric model. * refers to those metric parameters related with the crack damage.

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2.3.4 Monitoring network

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The monitoring network is a collection of different instances of a new family, representing each

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node of the system. This family has also been represented by means of patch-objects (Figure 6b),

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which are always attached to a main object, such as construction elements or assets. To represent

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the nodes, these patches are modelled by cylindrical disks of the same size. The information added

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to these objects refers to the parameters registered by each node (Figure 8). The current version

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of this family integrates 27 parameters including bioclimatic (temperature, CO₂, luminosity),

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structural (e.g. inclination or crack width) and biological (e.g. presence of xylophagous). Each

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node stores information of the manufacturer, installation date and maintenance protocols, as well.

Name ID Node		
Category Monitoring Network		
Parameter Name	IFC Type data	Notes
Geometric Data		
Radius	IFCReal	Example: 0.10 m
Identification Data		
Node ID	IFCInteger	Example: 8
Date Installation	IFCDate	Example: 11 / 01/2019
Connection Type	IFCText	Example: Zig-Bee
Monitoring parameter	IFCText	Example: C, S for CO ₂ and Solar radiation
Inspection Periods	IFCDate	Date of known inspections
Status	IFCInteger	Example: 1, 2, 3 depending of the KPI
Parameters Data (example of tow parameters)		
Temperature	IFCReal	Example: 21°
Humidity	IFCReal	Example: 25%

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Figure 8. Node family structure with the IFC parameters for the monitoring network.

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2.4 Integration of the monitoring data within the HBIM environment

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The data acquired by the monitoring network is processed following a workflow specifically

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designed to make periodic queries to the monitoring server (Figure 9a). The data of these queries

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

292 is encapsulated and transmitted through the use of a JSON file, which includes the node
 293 description attributes (id, location, description, dimensions, weight, date of installation and
 294 custom information provided by the manufacturer) as well as all the parameters showed in Section
 295 2.3.4. (Figure 9b). The data captured by each node is stored in a MySQL database that allows
 296 plotting graphs to analyse the evolution of specific parameters along the time. Moreover, the data
 297 can be exported into a tabulated format, i.e. an EXCEL file, to process it by an external software.

Figure 9. Connection of the monitoring network with the HBIM environment: a) general workflow;
 b) Structure of the MySQL database.

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301 It is worth mentioning that each object defined in the HBIM environment includes a label defined
302 as *Status* (Figure 7 and Figure 8). This field allows to classify the conservation risk of each
303 object according to its current bioclimatic condition. In this sense, the current version of the API
304 implements the KPI proposed by Corgnati et al. [25] (Eq.1). These KPI have been implemented
305 in the previous Service Level of the HeritageCARE method [29].

$$KPI = \frac{N_{in}}{N_{tot}} \quad (1)$$

306 where N_{in} represents the number of measurements within the defined tolerances and N_{tot} the total
307 number of measurements.

308 These KPI define the percentage of measurements in which the monitored parameter lies within
309 a required range of tolerances (Eq. 1). A value of 100 means a perfect match (all the measures are
310 within the limits). Meanwhile a value of 0 represents a total mismatch being all the measures out
311 of tolerance. If the value of the KPI is above 90%, the HBIM system assigns to the *Status* label a
312 value of 1 (low risk). If the value is below 90% but above 85%, the HBIM system assigns a value
313 of 2 (medium risk). Finally, if the value is below 85% the HBIM system assigns a value of 3 (high
314 risk).

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316 **2.5 Tolerances for the bioclimatic monitoring**

317 The preventive conservation of museums and libraries requires a rigorous control of the
318 bioclimatic conditions in order to maintain the assets, e.g. books, manuscripts or painting among
319 others, in optimal conditions. According to Pavlogeorgatos [23], the five main environmental
320 parameters that can promote the degradation of the assets placed in libraries are: i) temperature;
321 ii) relative humidity; iii) illumination; iv) atmospheric pollutant and; v) noise and vibrations. Out
322 of tolerance values in the first four parameters could promote the presence of chemical and
323 physical degradation processes. Meanwhile the last one could promote physical damages.

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325 From this variety of parameters previously shown, the proposed HBIM approach implements the
326 concept of KPI in three of the five fields in accordance with the nodes installed in the monitoring
327 network. In all of these indicators different types of tolerances were taken into consideration
328 according to the materials defined in the HBIM objects (Table 5 and Table 6). These set of
329 tolerances extend those proposed previously by Sánchez-Aparicio et al. [29], including specific
330 tolerances of the different materials presented on the library. Then, this parameter was used to
331 define the label *Status* of each object. Additionally, the system includes a KPI for the xylophagous
332 detector. In this case, only two values were included in the label *Status* [29] : i) 1 if the node does
333 not detect the presence of xylophagous and; ii) 3 if the node detects the presence of xylophagous.

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Table 5. Admissible tolerances for assets in accordance with its material. Adapted from Adcock [42].

Material	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)
Paper	18-22	40 – 55
Scroll	18-22	45 – 60
Leather	16-20	45 – 60
Textile	16-20	30 – 50
Wood	17-21	45 – 60
Metal works	18-22	15 – 55

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Table 6. Admissible levels of luminosity for different type of materials. Adapted from Sharif-Askari and Abu-Hijhel [43].

Object Type	Lux lumen/m²
Very Sensitive *	0 - 50
Sensitive **	0 - 200
Insensitive ***	0 - 300

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*Very sensitive: book, manuscript. **Sensitive: Oil / tempera painting, undyed leather

***Insensitive: Metal, ceramic, stone.

351 **3. Experimental results**

352

353 **3.1. Study case: The Historical Library of the University of Salamanca**

354

355 The General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca dates back to the XV century and
356 is part of the *Escuelas Mayores*, placed in the historical centre of Salamanca (Castilla y León,
357 Spain). The Library is located on the second floor, behind the main Plateresque style facade
358 (Figure 10), which is an emblematic symbol of the oldest Spanish University.

359

360

361

Figure 10. General Library of the University of Salamanca location.

362

363 The building has been modified several times since its creation in 1254, when the king Alfonso
364 X reorganized the academies. In the reorganization it was created the stationary house. During
365 the XV century, the manuscripts were moved to a specific room in the San Geronimo chapel,
366 inside the building of *Escuelas Mayores*. The General Historical Library was built between 1509
367 and 1526. In 1749, it was restructured according to the instructions of Andrés García de Quiñones,
368 and it has maintained its appearance since then (Figure 11). With respect to the architecture, the
369 Gothic door stands out. It was forged in 1526 with an arch carpanell, archivolt decorated with

370 plant and animal elements and closed with a Renaissance grille. The gallery is covered with a
371 lunette vault in the centre and a polygonal shape at its ends [44] (Figure 11a).

372 The library contains an extensive bibliographic collection formed by 483 incunabula, 2,774
373 manuscripts, and 62,000 printed volumes. All these elements have many different origins so, in
374 order to have them ordered, they are divided in different fields of knowledge. There are eight
375 categories: i) Literature; ii) Maps; iii) Language; iv) Natural; v) History; vi) Religion; vii)
376 Medicine-Science and Technique; viii) Laws and History. The codex *Las Virtuosas y Claras*
377 *Mujeres*, the incunabulum *Libro de Ajedrez*, *Libro del Buen Amor* or *the Appian's Cosmography*
378 stand out among the books contained in the library. All of them are stored in wooded Baroque
379 style shelves, designed by Manuel de Lara Churriguera [45]. Apart from the documents and
380 books, there are several celestial and armillary wooden spheres, tables, leather and wood chairs
381 and vitrines (Figure 11).

382
383 Figure 11. a) General view of the Library and arrangement of the shelves. b) Manuscript Room.
384 c) Table where several manuscripts are exhibited. d) Books and world globes.
385

386 Besides the Historical Library, there is a small *incunabulum* room that occupies the interior of the
387 Plateresque façade and holds manuscripts of the 11th century and the incunabula of the XV
388 century (Figure 11b). These books are organized in two themes of study: i) Canon Law and; ii)
389 Theology. This room is the old medieval ark of the university, initially used to keep money and,
390 later on, forbidden books.

391 **3.2 In-Field Works**

392 The in-field works were mainly focused on capturing the different type of information required
393 for define the HBIM. Three steps were carried out to this end: i) a visual inspection to improve
394 the knowledge about the conservation state of the Library and its assets; ii) a digitalization of the
395 Library by means of a WMMS and; iii) the installation of a wireless monitoring network.

396 *3.2.1 Inspection of the Library*

397 The visual inspection of the Library was carried out following the guidelines proposed by the
398 HeritageCare initiative [27,28]. Specifically, the first and second level of inspection protocols
399 were applied. In order to maintaining a common metric during the survey, a mobile app was used,
400 allowing to capture all the necessary data by means of standardized checklists.

401 On the one hand, the first level of inspection allows to obtain a rapid condition screening
402 of the conservation status of the building. During the inspection, a conservation
403 assessment of each construction element was carried out as well. This assessment
404 included an analysis of the damages presented on the elements following the approach
405 proposed by Masciotta et al.[27]. Each damage is defined by the following variables: i)
406 the class of damage; ii) the condition grade; iii) a short description of the damage; iv) its
407 extension along the construction element and; v) a risk assessment. The result of this
408 inspection allows identifying different types of damage located in the following
409 construction elements: i) structural deep cracks on the bearing wall and on the lunette
410 vault due to the initial accommodation of the structure; ii) moist areas on the vault's

411 keystone coming from the timber roof and iii) some discolorations on the timber floor.
412 Apart from these damages the inspection highlighted the absence of UV filter on the
413 windows, which could promote the photodegradation of some assets as well as
414 inappropriate air ventilation in the *incunabulum* room (Figure 11b).

415 The second level of inspection concerned the conservation assessment of the assets
416 presented in the Library by following a similar protocol to the previous one. Due to the
417 huge amount of assets, only the most representative ones were inspected: i) two vitrines;
418 ii) two chairs; iii) one Earth Globe and; iv) twenty-one exceptional books from the
419 different knowledge areas (within its associated shelves). The result of this inspection
420 allowed identifying the different materials presented on the assets as well as the presence
421 of some discolouration and deposits.

422 3.2.2 Digitalization of the library

423 The Zeb-Revo Wearable Mobile Mapping System from GeoSlam® [33]. was used for digitalizing
424 the library. The Zeb-Revo system consists of a rotatory head that comprises a 2D laser scan head
425 and an IMU. The head is connected to a processing unit, which is carried by the user in a backpack,
426 allowing the digitalization of large spaces while walking through them. The information captured
427 by the scan head and the IMU are finally integrated to create a 3D point cloud by means of a full-
428 SLAM algorithm [16], providing an accuracy that ranges from 1 to 3 cm.

429 In order to avoid mistakes and get optimal results, the suggestions of di-Filippo et al. [14] were
430 followed, such as: i) remove any disturbing object; ii) leave doors between different room open
431 to make easy the path; iii) add items to help the algorithm works in those places where the
432 geometry is very similar and with no significant changes and; iv) the designed path should be a
433 loop, starting and finishing in the same point, in order to let the SLAM algorithm adjust errors.

434 Once the environment was prepared, the digitalization was made in a unique loop with a constant
435 speed to have the same density in all the point cloud and being especially careful in transitions
436 over the doors. For the present case study, 14 minutes were invested to obtain the 3D point cloud

437 of the whole Library (Figure 12): eight minutes to capture the data and six to solve the SLAM
438 problem. The point cloud obtained had a total of 15 million of points.

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440
441

Figure 12. Data collection path executed for the digitalization of the Library

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443

3.2.3 Monitoring system

444 The final stage of the in-field works involved the installation of a monitoring network. A
445 total of 39 wireless nodes were placed along the Library (Figure 13 and Figure 14): i) 23
446 for monitoring humidity and temperature; ii) 1 for detecting the presence of people; iii) 8
447 for monitoring luminosity; iv) 2 for monitoring CO₂ in the environment; v) 2 for
448 monitoring solar radiation; vi) 2 for monitoring the presence of xylophagous; vii) and 1
449 methodological station. In addition to the two local nodes, there was a central node. This
450 node sent the information to the central computer (Figure 3). The data thrown by each
451 node can be consulted online, providing real time values (Figure 15). The monitoring
452 system is active since July 2019.

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Figure 13. Nodes distribution in the Library

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Figure 14. Nodes installation in the Library.

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Figure 15. Real time data captured by the nodes 17 and 18.

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3.3 HBIM Environment

467

468 The HBIM of the Library was implemented in Revit from Autodesk®. All the features shown in

469 Section 2.3 were included in this framework by means of an in-house plugin named Heritage 5.0

470 This plugin allows assigning different families to the geometries, with specific LoI, storing and

471 processing the different data captured by the monitoring network as well as calculating the KPI.

472 The geometrical model of the Library was obtained by using a semi-automatic reverse engineering

473 procedure. This approach starts with the triangulation of the WMMS point cloud, using to this

474 end a 3D Delaunay triangulation. Then the mesh model is processed by applying the stages

475 proposed by Attene [46], which incorporates several automatic and sequential stages: i) a hole

476 filling stage using the radial basis function [47]; ii) a repair stage based on the minimum threshold

477 distance algorithm [48]; iii) a topological and geometric noise removal stage through the use of

478 local re-triangulation methods and anti-aliased Laplacians filters [49]. After this processing stage

479 the mesh is modelled in order to create a suitable solid model for BIM purposes. For basic shapes

480 (e.g. walls or spheres) the RANSAC Shape Detector algorithm was used [50]. For complex shapes

481 a section-based modelling procedure was applied as suggests Sánchez-Aparicio et al. 2019 [40].

482 All these stages were complemented with standard reverse engineering procedures such as the

483 extrusion for modelling the thickness of different elements (e.g. the walls or the vaults), as well

484 as Boolean operators for creating the windows. Figure 16 shows a comparative study between

485 several solid models and their corresponding point clouds. As could be observed, the reverse

486 engineering procedure carried out allows to reproduce with an acceptable accuracy the different

487 constructive elements and assets placed within the Library. The largest discrepancies take places

488 on those parts with complex decorative elements which were considered not relevant for the

489 preventive conservation policies of the Library. These decorative elements were included in the

490 information tab of the families (see Section 2.3).

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Figure 16. Discrepancies between the original point cloud and the solid model: a) vault of the Library; b) an armillary wooden sphere and; c) a shelf at the entrance of the Library.

495

The different solid models generated (Figure 17) were introduced within the BIM environment, using the Heritage 5.0 Plugin to assign the same information attributes to each specific family.

496

497

The LoI of each asset, node or damage include several common parameters between them (i.e.

498

Condition grade, Inspection Periods, Short Description, Asset ID or Status), which have different

499

values in each particular family. The Heritage 5.0 Plugin allows to add all the common attributes

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to the desired family in an automatic way, making this task easier and faster (Figure 18). The data

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introduced of each family was obtained from the technical inspection (see Section 3.2.1).

502

Additionally, the damages and nodes from the monitoring network were imported by means of

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path-based families (Figure 19).

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Figure 17. Geometrical model of the Library: a) workflow; b) detail of the final solid model.

a)

b)

Asset Category	Furniture
Asset Code	115
Asset Name	World Globe
Changes, modification...	2017
Date/period of crafting...	XVIII Century
Inspection Periods	6 months
Legal Category of Prot...	
Location Information	
Owner Contact	Plaza Escuelas May
Owner Name	Universidad de Sala
Short Description	
Style	Wood

c)

Text	
Damage Class	Discolouration and Depo
Damage Sub Class	Discolouration
Damage Sub Sub Class	Moist Area
Condition Classification	Fair
Symptoms	Minor Symptoms
Condition Grade	In Fair condition
Description	Detected Moist
Afected Area (%)	10 %
Risk Assesment	Intermediate
Urgency Risk Classifica	Intermediate Term
Materials	
Color	Damage Intermediate

d)

Text	
Node ID	8
Date Installation	11/03/2018
Connection Type	Zig
Monitoring Parameter	Temperature; Humidity
Inspection Periods	Year
Condition Grade	1
Status	1
Others	
Humidity	57.000
Luminosity	72
Temperature	9.40 °C

Figure 18. Application of families to the different solid models created: a) assigning a new family; b) movable asset; c) damage observed in the wall and d) node of the monitoring network.

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Figure 19. General view of the HBIM model on which is possible to observe the path-based families used to represent the damages and nodes of the monitoring network.

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3.3.1 Checking the monitoring data

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The monitoring network was connected to the HBIM by means of node families according to the disposition shown in Figure 13. The information shown in each node object corresponds with the latest data received from the *JSON* request. Complementarily, the system stores all this information on its own database (Figure 9). This allows to plot timeline graphs, thereby assessing the temporal evolution of specific parameters. The user can decide which node and interval is plotted. All this information can be exported in *.CSV* format (Figure 20).

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Figure 20. Appearance of the Heritage 5.0 plugin when the user consults the data of one node.

525

526 Additionally, the data stored in the database is used to compute the KPI on each asset of the
527 HBIM. In this case the user can decide the range of dates included in the computation of the KPI.
528 It is worth mentioning that the plugin computes different KPI for the same node according to the
529 different materials presented on the assets (see Section 2.4). Finally, the nearest KPI is assigned
530 to each asset. This KPI is introduced within the *Status* label as an integer value which varies from
531 1 (green) to 3 (red). Each family has a *Status* label per measured parameter (i.e Status for
532 temperature or Status for relative humidity). In those cases on which the family is integrated by
533 different types of materials, and thus by different ranges of admissible tolerances, the system uses
534 the most unfavourable KPIs to colorize the family (Figure 21).

535

536 Figure 21. Computation of the KPI for objects with different materials. Green colour represents a KPI
537 above 90 % and Status = 1. Yellow colour represents a KPI between 85% and 90% and Status = 2.

538

539 Under the basis previously shown different KPI evaluations were carried out on the Library,
540 considering as the reference period one month. Table 7 and Figure 22 shows the results of
541 computing the KPI for one cold month such as February. As could be observed, most of the assets
542 are plotted in red which suggest that the bioclimatic conditions could promote some damage on
543 the assets. In all the cases the temperature ranges are not within the acceptable ranges defined in
544 Section 2.5, showing an average value of 12.2 °C with a minimum value of 10.9°C and a maximum
545 temperature of 16°C. For this month the relative humidity has an average value of 62% with a

546 minimum value of 58 % and a maximum value of 64%, exceeding in most of the cases the
547 admissible ranges (Table 5). Regarding the luminosity, all the nodes of the monitoring network
548 showed optimal values (up to 95%) even for very sensitive assets such as books or manuscripts.
549

550 Table 7. Results of the KPI computation for temperature and humidity during February. Right KPI comes
551 from the temperature evaluation. Left KPI comes from the relative humidity evaluation. Null values refer to situations
552 in which all the measurements are out of the recommended tolerances.

Type of material	Node			
	07	15	17	18
Paper	0.00 / 1.46	0.00 / 0.00	0.00 / 0.00	21.63 / 0.00
Leather	98.07 / 0.35	0.00 / 0.00	16.38 / 0.00	46.59 / 0.00
Textile	0.00 / 0.35	0.00 / 0.00	0.00 / 0.00	1.41 / 0.00
Wood	98.07 / 0.83	0.00 / 0.00	16.38 / 0.00	46.66 / 0.00
Metal works	0.00 / 1.46	0.00 / 0.00	0.00 / 0.00	21.93 / 0.00

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554

555 Similar results were obtained for one warm moth (July). In this case the average temperature
556 exceeds the recommended upper bound with an average, maximum and minimum values of
557 25.4°C, 27.9 °C and 18.6°C respectively. These values of temperature could accelerate the
558 degradation of the assets as well as becoming uncomfortable for visitors. The relative humidity
559 during this month was also outside the admissible range, with an average value of 45 %. This low
560 value could can cause assets to become dry and brittle.

561 The results obtained for both months, February and July, corroborates the necessity of a HVAC
562 (Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning) control systems for minimizing the possible damage
563 of the assets. This appreciation is in line with the suggestion done during the inspection carried
564 out in Section 3.2.1.

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Figure 22: HBIM model with the KPI plotted: a) general view; b) Computation of the KPI for temperature conditions; c) Computation of the KPI for Humidity conditions And; d) Computation of the KPI for Luminosity conditions. White circles represent the nodes position. The assets plotted in green has a *Status* label of 1, assets in yellow has a *Status* of 2 and assets in yellow a *Status* of 3.

572

3.3.2 Conservation assessment and damage

573

574 Apart from plotting in a graph the KPI of each asset, the plugin allows plotting different

575 parameters of relevance for the preventive conservation of the site, such as the urgency risk. Due

576 to the absence of UV filter in the windows, as well as an adequate ventilation system in the

577 *incunabulum* room, the conservation status of the assets was fixed to fair, implying a mid-term

578 urgency risk (Figure 23a). Figure 23b shows the plot in the case of not considering this issue. In

579 this case, some of the assets show a good conservation status (green colour). Complementarily,

580 the plugin highlights the assets with a specific damage (Figure 23c).

a)

b)

c)

582 Figure 23: Graphical plots within the HBIM model: a) Urgency risk considering the absence of
583 ultraviolet (UV) filter and a proper ventilation system; b) urgency risk according with the conservation
584 status of the assets and; c) assets with presence of discolouration.

585

586 3.4 Discussion of the approaches adopted for the creation of the HBIM model

587

588 This section is devoted to discussing the impact of the different approaches adopted in the
589 proposed HBIM methodology.

590 Regarding the geometrical aspect, the use of a WMMS proves to be a really efficient solution for
591 the digitalization of heritage sites. This device requires just only 14 minutes to obtain the whole
592 point cloud of the Library, outperforming the time estimated for a terrestrial laser scanner to
593 digitalize the same area, which could be estimated in 225 min. Apart of this, the flexibility of the
594 system allows to obtain data in complex areas such as corridors (Figure 11d). The density of the
595 data obtained by the WMMS solution allows to create families with a LoD of 300 (Table 3). This
596 LoD could be considered enough for defining nodes, damages and assets. In the case of nodes,
597 this threshold is irrelevant in comparison with the LoI since is a family devoted to capturing the
598 monitoring data. However, this threshold has higher impact in the families that define the damages
599 and the assets. On the one hand, the LoD adopted for the damages allows to define it in terms of
600 urgency, position and orientation by means of patch-based families with different sizes in
601 accordance with their severity. The extension and other relevant metric values are considered in
602 the LoI. This approach allows not only the integration and monitoring of the evolution of the
603 damages in a simple way, but also having a rapid screening of the impact of each one (Figure 19).
604 On the other hand, the LoD adopted for the assets families does not include the most detailed
605 ornamental parts which are included in the LoI by means of the historical data as well as a detailed
606 photographic survey. The adoption of this threshold is in line with the current necessities of the
607 Library in terms of preventive conservation. According to this, the main advantage of adopting
608 a low LoD relies in the possibility of using WMMS system which provided an acceptable point
609 cloud for a LoD of 300. In case of requiring the modelling of ornamental parts it is recommended

610 the use of a high-density laser scanner system (e.g. triangulation lasers) or even photogrammetric
611 approaches which provides detailed point cloud of local areas of the asset. The use of this
612 approaches will increase the time spent during the digitalization campaign and during the
613 modelling stage.

614 The use of KPI and operational thresholds in conjunction with the LoI of the families (in special
615 the material definition) and a colour-grade scale allows to synthetize the big data coming from
616 the monitoring network. This combination creates an easy-reading and robust screening of the
617 climatic conditions of the assets placed within the Library, which depends of the material
618 presented in the asset (Fig. 22). In case of requiring a detailed information about the evolution of
619 the parameters, the proposed HBIM approach suggest the use of CSV files.

620 **4 Conclusions**

621 This paper presents an HBIM approach for the preventive conservation of historical buildings.
622 With this aim, the methodology exploits the latest advances in 3D digitalization, inspection
623 protocols and advanced monitoring networks.

624 The wearable mobile mapping system pops up due to its lightweight and flexibility compared to
625 traditional approaches, such as photogrammetry and laser scanning. This device just requires to
626 perform a close-loop path to capture the whole scene as well as to compensate a possible error
627 accumulation. The density of the point cloud obtained by this device, within the use of reverse
628 engineering approaches, allows modelling the different elements required to define the HBIM
629 model, such as the assets. To this end, the method applies a post-processing approach for meshing
630 the WMMS point cloud. This mesh is then used as geometrical base for reverse engineering,
631 allowing to obtain a suitable solid model of the construction by means of the use of sections, Loft
632 surfaces, extrusions and Boolean operators. This approach allows to obtain, in a quick way, BIM
633 families with a LoD of 300. This LoD could be increased (i.e. modelling the ornamental parts),
634 through the use of additional remote sensing strategies such as triangulation scanners or
635 photogrammetric approaches for modelling ornamental features.

636 The low LoD applied in the different families of the HBIM model is complemented by a high
637 LoI. Within this context, the method proposes the use of the standardized inspection protocol
638 proposed by the HeritageCare initiative. This protocol allows the appropriate definition of the
639 different damage presented on the assets as well as the urgency risk. All this information is
640 complemented by images that allow defining different details that are not modelled.

641 Complementarily to the previously mentioned approaches, the methodology suggests the use of
642 an advance monitoring network that enables capturing different variables of relevance, i.e.
643 environmental variables, used to control the microclimate of the assets. This data can be stored in
644 a database that is directly linked to the HBIM model, allowing to plot graphs as well as to export
645 data in a universal format, i.e. the CSV file.

646 All the information generated by the different methods is integrated into a unique environment
647 by means of the development of an in-house plugin named Heritage 5.0, thereby generating a
648 multidisciplinary environment that stands out due to its interoperability. This interoperability
649 increases work efficiency between the different agents involved in the preventive conservation of
650 heritage buildings. Apart of fusing this information, the plugin allows exploiting the data
651 contained in each family to compute the so-called KPI in accordance with the different materials
652 presented on the assets. This KPI is plotted in a user-friendly way using a colour-grade scale.
653 Moreover, it could be used to activate any intervention that could facilitate the management of
654 the site. This strategy is also applied for the urgency risk as well as the damage, displaying the
655 conservation status and environmental conditions of the assets as images.

656 This approach has been applied to one of the most representative Spanish heritage places. It
657 allowed identifying deficiencies that could promote the degradation of the assets, such as the
658 absence of UV filter on the windows or the inappropriate ventilation system in the incunabulum
659 room.

660 Future works will focus on improving the current version of the tool by adding additional features
661 for the preventive conservation, such as: i) the possibility of plotting technical reports about the
662 conservation state of the site and assets; ii) the integration of structural features that allow

663 evaluating the structural stability of heritage sites by means of HBIM approaches and advanced
664 numerical evaluations; iii) the development of approaches that follow the conservation of heritage
665 sites along time and; iv) the integration of CFD approaches for evaluating the distribution of
666 bioclimatic parameters along the heritage sites. Therefore, new information will be added to the
667 families, such as the transmittance of each layer.

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680

681 **References**

682

683 [1] R.C. Matulionis, J.C. Freitag, Preventive maintenance of buildings, Van Nostrand
684 Reinhold, New York, 1991. ISBN:0-442-31866-9.

685 [2] P. Jouan, P. Hallot, Digital Twin: A HBIM-based methodology to support preventive
686 conservation of historic assets through heritage significance awareness, in: 27th CIPA
687 International Symposium “Documenting the Past for a Better Future,” Ávila, Spain, 2019:
688 pp.609-615. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-609-2019>.

689 [3] M. Murphy, E. Mcgovern, S. Pavia, Historic building information modelling (HBIM),
690 Structural Survey. 27 (2009) pp.311-327. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02630800910985108>.

691 [4] A. Mol, M. Cabaleiro, H.S. Sousa, J.M. Branco, HBIM for storing life-cycle data
692 regarding decay and damage in existing timber structures, Automation in Construction.
693 117 (2020) p. 103262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103262>.

694 [5] R. Brumana, S. della Torre, D. Oreni, M. Previtali, L. Cantini, L. Barazzetti, A. Franchi,
695 F. Banfi, HBIM challenge among the paradigm of complexity, tools and preservation: the
696 Basilica di Collemaggio 8 years after the earthquake (L’Aquila), in: 26th International
697 CIPA Symposium, Ottawa, Canada, 2017: pp.97-104. [https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-
698 archives-XLII-2-W5-97-2017](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W5-97-2017).

699 [6] N. Bruno, R. Roncella, A restoration oriented HBIM system for cultural heritage
700 documentation: the case study of Parma Cathedral, in: ISPRS TC II Mid-Term Symposium
701 “Towards Photogrammetry 2020,” Riva del Garda, Italy, 2018: pp.171-178.
702 <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-171-2018>.

703 [7] P. Crespi, A. Franchi, P. Ronca, N. Giordano, M. Scamardo, G. Gusmeroli, G.
704 Schiantarelli, From BIM to FEM: the analysis of an historical masonry building, WIT

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

705 Transactions on The Built Environment. 149 (2015) pp.581-592.

706 <https://doi.org/10.2495/BIM150471>.

707 [8] A. Cali, Â. do Valle, P. Dias de Moraes, Building Information Modeling and structural
708 analysis in the knowledge path of a historical construction, in: Structural Analysis of
709 Historical Constructions, Cusco, Peru, 2018: pp.2071-2079.
710 https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99441-3_222.

711 [9] S. Bruno, M. de Fino, F. Fatiguso, Historic Building Information Modelling: performance
712 assessment for diagnosis-aided information modelling and management, Automation in
713 Construction. 86 (2018) pp.256-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2017.11.009>.

714 [10] H.-M. Cheng, W.-B. Yang, Y.-N. Yen, BIM applied in historical building documentation
715 and refurbishing, in: 25th International CIPA Symposium, Taipei, Taiwan, 2015: pp.85-
716 90. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W7-85-2015>.

717 [11] L. Barazzetti, F. Banfi, R. Brumana, D. Oreni, M. Previtali, F. Roncoroni, HBIM and
718 augmented information: towards a wider user community of image and range-based
719 reconstructions, in: 25th International CIPA Symposium, Taipei, Taiwan, 2015: pp.35-
720 42. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W7-35-2015>

721 [12] M. Murphy, E. McGovern, S. Pavia, Historic Building Information Modelling - Adding
722 intelligence to laser and image based surveys of European classical architecture, ISPRS
723 Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing. 76 (2013) pp.89-102.
724 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2012.11.006>.

725 [13] M. Godinho, R. Machete, M. Ponte, A.P. Falcão, A.B. Gonçalves, R. Bento, BIM as a
726 resource in heritage management: An application for the National Palace of Sintra,
727 Portugal, Journal of Cultural Heritage. 43 (2020) pp.153-162.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2019.11.010>.

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

- 729 [14] A. di Filippo, L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, S. Barba, J.A. Martín-Jiménez, R. Mora, D.G.
730 Aguilera, Use of a Wearable Mobile Laser System in Seamless Indoor 3D Mapping of a
731 Complex Historical Site, Remote Sensing. 10 (2018) pp.1-19.
732 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10121897>.
- 733 [15] M.Á. Maté-González, L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, C. Sáez Blázquez, P. Carrasco García, D.
734 Álvarez-Alonso, M. de Andrés-Herrero, J.C. García-Davalillo, D. González-Aguilera, M.
735 Hernández Ruiz, L. Jordá Bordehore, C. López Carnicero, R. Mora, On the Combination
736 of Remote Sensing and Geophysical Methods for the Digitalization of the San Lázaro
737 Middle Paleolithic Rock Shelter (Segovia, Central Iberia, Spain), Remote Sensing. 11
738 (2019) p. 2035. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11172035>.
- 739 [16] S. Thrun, Simultaneous localization and mapping, in: Robotics and Cognitive Approaches
740 to Spatial Mapping, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2007: pp.13-41. ISBN: 978-3-540-
741 75388-9.
- 742 [17] L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, B. Conde, M.A. Maté-González, R. Mora, M. Sánchez-Aparicio,
743 J. García-Álvarez, D. González-Aguilera, A comparative study between WMMS and TLS
744 for the stability analysis of the San Pedro Church Barrel vault by means of the finite
745 element method, in: 27th CIPA International Symposium “Documenting the Past for a
746 Better Future,” Ávila, Spain, 2019: pp.1047-1054. [https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-1047-2019)
747 [XLII-2-W15-1047-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-1047-2019).
- 748 [18] F. Diara, F. Rinaudo, From reality to parametric models of cultural heritage assets for
749 HBIM, in: 27th CIPA International Symposium “Documenting the Past for a Better
750 Future,” Ávila, Spain, 2019: pp.413-419. [https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-413-2019)
751 [W15-413-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-413-2019).
- 752 [19] R. Brumana, S. della Torre, M. Previtali, L. Barazzetti, L. Cantini, D. Oreni, F. Banfi,
753 Generative HBIM modelling to embody complexity (LOD, LOG, LOA, LOI): surveying,

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

754 preservation, site intervention—the Basilica di Collemaggio (L’Aquila), Applied
755 Geomatics. 10 (2018) pp.545-567. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12518-018-0233-3>.

756 [20] R. Quattrini, R. Pierdicca, C. Morbidoni, Knowledge-based data enrichment for HBIM:
757 Exploring high-quality models using the semantic-web, Journal of Cultural Heritage. 28
758 (2017) pp.129-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2017.05.004>.

759 [21] M. Azenha, G. Sousa, J. Matos, J. Sena-Cruz, V. Brito, Integrated application of advanced
760 surveying techniques and BIM for inspection and asset management of reinforced concrete
761 bridges, in: International Conference on Interdisciplinary Approaches for Cement-Based
762 Materials and Structural Concrete, 2018.
763 <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/bitstream/1822/58508/1/%5B81%5D.pdf> (accessed
764 September 1, 2020).

765 [22] M.G. Masciotta, L.F. Ramos, P.B. Lourenço, J.A.C. Matos, Development of key
766 performance indicators for the structural assessment of heritage buildings, in: 8th
767 European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring, EWSHM 2016, 2016: pp.606-617.
768 <https://www.ndt.net/search/docs.php3?showForm=off&id=20121>. (accessed September
769 1, 2020).

770 [23] G. Pavlogeorgatos, Environmental parameters in museums, Building and Environment. 38
771 (2003) pp.1457-1462. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323\(03\)00113-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323(03)00113-6).

772 [24] M. Bacci, C. Cucci, A.A. Mencaglia, A.G. Mignani, Innovative sensors for environmental
773 monitoring in museums, Sensors. 8 (2008) pp.1984-2005.
774 <https://doi.org/10.3390/s8031984>.

775 [25] S.P. Corgnati, V. Fabi, M. Filippi, A methodology for microclimatic quality evaluation in
776 museums: Application to a temporary exhibit, Building and Environment. 44 (2009)
777 pp.1253-1260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.09.012>.

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

- 778 [26] M. de la P. Diulio, P. Mercader-Moyano, A.F. Gómez, The influence of the envelope in
779 the preventive conservation of books and paper records. Case study: Libraries and archives
780 in La Plata, Argentina, *Energy and Buildings*. 183 (2019) pp.727-738.
781 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.11.048>.
- 782 [27] M.G. Masciotta, M.J. Morais, L.F. Ramos, D. V. Oliveira, L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, D.
783 González-Aguilera, A Digital-based Integrated Methodology for the Preventive
784 Conservation of Cultural Heritage: The Experience of HeritageCare Project, *International*
785 *Journal of Architectural Heritage*. (2019) pp.1-20.
786 <https://doi.org/10.1080/15583058.2019.1668985>.
- 787 [28] L.F. Ramos, M.G. Masciotta, M.J. Morais, M. Azenha, T. Ferreira, E.B. Pereira, P.B.
788 Lourenço, HeritageCARE: preventive conservation of built cultural heritage in the South-
789 West Europe, in: K. van Balen, A. Vandesande (Eds.), *Innovative Built Heritage Models*,
790 CRC Press, London, United Kingdom, 2018: pp.135-142.
- 791 [29] L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, M.G. Masciotta, J. García-Alvarez, L.F. Ramos, D. v. Oliveira,
792 J.A. Martín-Jiménez, D. González-Aguilera, P. Monteiro, Web-GIS approach to
793 preventive conservation of heritage buildings, *Automation in Construction*. 118 (2020)
794 103304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103304>.
- 795 [30] The British Standards Institution, PAS 198: 2012 Specification for managing
796 environmental conditions for cultural collections, 2012. ISBN: 9780580713156.
- 797 [31] GeoSLAM, ZEB Go - GeoSLAM, (2020). <https://geoslam.com/solutions/zeb-go/>
798 (accessed September 1, 2020).
- 799 [32] M. Quigley, B. Gerkey, K. Conley, J. Faust, T. Foote, J. Leibs, E. Berger, R. Wheeler, A.
800 Ng, ROS: an open-source Robot Operating System, *ICRA Workshop on Open Source*
801 *Software*. 3 (2009) 5. Available at

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

802 <https://www.willowgarage.com/sites/default/files/icraoss09-ROS.pdf>. (accessed
803 September 1, 2020).

804 [33] Survey REVolution. Introducing the ZEB-REVO mobile indoor mapping system., 2017.
805 Available at <https://surveyequipment.com/assets/index/download/id/532/> (accessed
806 September 1, 2020).

807 [34] M. Chiriac, D. Basulto, E. López, J.C. Prieto, J. Castillo, A. Collado, The MHS system as
808 an active tool for the preventive conservation of cultural heritage, 2013. Available at
809 http://www.arscivilis.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/T1P7_MHS_3.pdf (accessed
810 September 18, 2020).

811 [35] M. Azenha, M.G. Masciotta, G. Sousa, C. Alarcon, M.J.C. Morais, J. Sena-Cruz, D. V.
812 Oliveira, Building Information Modelling (BIM) no contexto dos edificios antigos, in:
813 Universidade Nova de Lisboa. Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia (Ed.), Conferência
814 Internacional Sobre Reabilitação de Estruturas Antigas de Alvenaria, 2018.
815 <http://hdl.handle.net/1822/58488>.

816 [36] P. Barnes, N. Davies, BIM in Principle and in Practice, Ice Publishing, 2015. ISBN
817 9780727760920.

818 [37] American Institute of Architects, AIA Document G202-2013: Project Building
819 Information Modeling Protocol Form, 2013. Available at
820 <https://www.aiacontracts.org/contract-documents/19016-project-bim-protocol>. (accessed
821 September 1, 2020).

822 [38] BuildingSMART Spain, Guía de usuarios BIM. Documento 14- BIM aplicado al
823 Patrimonio Cultural, 2018. Available at [https://www.buildingsmart.es/recursos/guías-](https://www.buildingsmart.es/recursos/guías-ubim)
824 [ubim](https://www.buildingsmart.es/recursos/guías-ubim) (accessed September 1, 2020).

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

- 825 [39] Á. Bautista-De Castro, L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, P. Carrasco-García, L.F. Ramos, D.
826 González-Aguilera, A multidisciplinary approach to calibrating advanced numerical
827 simulations of masonry arch bridges, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*. 129
828 (2019) pp.337-365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymsp.2019.04.043>.
- 829 [40] L.J. Sánchez-Aparicio, Á. Bautista-De Castro, B. Conde, P. Carrasco, L.F. Ramos, Non-
830 destructive means and methods for structural diagnosis of masonry arch bridges,
831 *Automation in Construction*. 104 (2019) pp.360-382.
832 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.04.021>.
- 833 [41] G. Sousa, M. Azenha, J. Matos, V. Brito, Implementação BIM no contexto de inspeção e
834 gestão da manutenção de obras de arte em betão armado: proposta de metodologia e
835 aplicação piloto, in: 2º Congresso Português de Building Information Modelling, 2018:
836 pp.519-528. Available at
837 <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/bitstream/1822/58486/1/%5B62%5D.pdf>. (accessed
838 September 1, 2020).
- 839 [42] E.P. Adcock, M.-T. Varlamoff, V. Kremp, *IFLA: Principles for the care and handling of*
840 *library material*, United States; France, 1998. ISBN: 2912743001.
- 841 [43] H. Sharif-Askari, B. Abu-Hijleh, Review of museums’ indoor environment conditions
842 studies and guidelines and their impact on the museums’ artifacts and energy consumption,
843 *Building and Environment*. 143 (2018) pp.186-195.
844 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.07.012>.
- 845 [44] A. Rodríguez G. de Ceballos, *Guía artística de Salamanca*, Ediciones Lancia, Leon, 2005.
846 ISBN:9788481771039.
- 847 [45] J.L. Díaz Segovia, M.T. Paliza Monduate, *Salamanca, Patrimonio de la Humanidad*, 1ª
848 Edición, Turimagen Ediciones, Madrid, 1997. ISBN: 9788492239702.

“This paper can be found at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103449>”

- 849 [46] M. Attene, A lightweight approach to repairing digitized polygon meshes, *The Visual*
850 *Computer*. 26 (2010) pp.1393-1406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-010-0416-3>.
- 851 [47] J.W. Branch, F. Prieto, P. Boulanger, Automatic hole-filling of triangular meshes using
852 local radial basis function, in: *Third International Symposium on 3D Data Processing,*
853 *Visualization, and Transmission (3DPVT'06)*, IEEE Computer Society, Chapel Hill, NC,
854 2006: pp. 727–734. <https://doi.org/10.1109/3DPVT.2006.33>.
- 855 [48] M. Attene, B. Falcidieno, ReMESH: An interactive environment to edit and repair triangle
856 meshes, in: *IEEE International Conference on Shape Modeling and Applications 2006*
857 *(SMI 2006)*, Matsushima, Japan, 2006: pp.41-47. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMI.2006.29>.
- 858 [49] I. Guskov, Z.J. Wood, Topological Noise Removal, in: *Graphics Interface Proceedings,*
859 *Ottawa, Canada, 2001: pp.19-44. Available at*
860 https://digitalcommons.calpoly.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1214&context=csse_fac
861 (accessed September 17, 2020).
- 862 [50] R. Schnabel, R. Wahl, R. Klein, Efficient RANSAC for point-cloud shape detection, in:
863 *Computer Graphics Forum, Oxford, UK, 2007: pp.214-226.*
864 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8659.2007.01016.x>.

865